

CHALLENGES OF ECONOMIC GLOBALISATION IN HEALTHCARE CONSIDERING HEALTHCARE COOPERATIVES AS RESPONSE

Milorad Stamenovic

Inventis CTC, Republic of Serbia

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with actual economic globalizations trends and its influence on healthcare systems, with specific intention on elaborating several issues in respect of Serbian healthcare system and its economic implications, but also its implications for other stakeholders (e.g. patients). Economical globalization is widely growing, mainly through process of liberalization of markets with eminence support of international financial and non financial organizations. Implication of neoliberalism and globalization on healthcare requires further restructuring of healthcare system and its inevitable model change. The health system in Serbia has not been set up so that the patient is in the focus of interest. On the one hand, the state does not invest in health care as much as is necessary to meet the needs of the insured, while on the other hand, the funds invested are not used in the optimal way. This paper discuss issues potential responses that could be saw in Healthcare cooperatives as a private ownership model.

Keywords: *Economic globalization, healthcare issues in globalization, healthcare system in Serbia*

1. INTRODUCTION

By satisfying curiosity and asking for answers to a number of questions, a person continually finds the answers he asked for and those he accidentally encountered. The causally connected, today's northern and southern hemisphere correlate with each other through a variety of ways and types of connections. Due to technical and technological development, the globalization of all forms of social connections, the planet Earth becomes one common entity, nowadays rounded off from the social aspect as well. The development of technology during the 20th and 21st centuries significantly contributes to further networking and function of the planet as a whole. Globalization is, by definition, a process, which is defined in some ways by the economic ideology of neo-liberalism (even the term global neo-liberalism is being criticized by some authors), it undoubtedly influences the further economic progress of humanity, while it is inspired by the argument of economic ideology. The history of neo-liberalism as today's leading economic ideology is not long enough to draw the final conclusions, but it is of great importance to analyze the flows and impacts of this economic ideology in the context of market development and liberalization (Stamenovic, Gulan,Dragas 2017). Globalization as a process (especially economic) and neoliberalism as ideology, cause deep and complex changes in the very nature of our society, bringing new opportunities and new risks. In addition, the effects of globalization are a growing concern for our health, and there is a growing problem of sustainable development (Stamenovic, Gulan,Dragas 2017). Market liberalization is certainly one of the most important processes that contributed to the acceleration of globalization and especially economic ones. Historically, the development of the market was preconditioned by the research of new geographic locations (new markets), but also by the development of production facilities in developed capitalist societies in the past. In Europe, organized markets developed much later than in the US. With the outbreak of World War I, countries abolished classical convertibility and passed on a paper standard, which allowed them to increase money printing to finance the needs of war, completely independent of the movement and size of gold reserves. It is worth mentioning that the ideas of Max Weber contributed significantly to the creation of an adequate "ambience" for the further development of modern capitalism, where the capitalist spirit and Protestant ethics are actually related to the notion of achievement, which

further defines the "society of achievements" and high developmental motivation, but also prosperity society. Therefore, on the basis of this, the distinction between motivated and prosperous societies and those that are backward is made. This concept is also determining healthcare in modern society. The World Health Organization defines health as a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, not only as a lack of sickness and incapacity, where the right to health is interpreted as the right to enjoy various forms of assistance, products, services and conditions necessary to achieve the highest possible standard of health. On the other hand, citizens' concern for public affairs and the common good stems from the fact that it belongs to everyone and should be given to everyone, through the process of redistribution of power and not to some, oligarchies. However, health transformation is a process in progress, a process parallel with the development of society. The process of globalization is also underway. Mechanisms for the implementation of globalization (some international institutions, NGOs, etc.) work with the goal of accelerating globalization as a process. More and more loud are the opponents of this process that affect all areas of society, however, the most pressing issues of economic nature in the process of globalization - for example, studying the legality of the global economy, capital flows, restructuring of ever larger markets, the impact of foreign investment - that's all one face of globalization. It is very important to look at all the processes of globalization separately but also together, as a whole, and try to approximate further movements in order to eliminate potential risks in a timely - preventive, and not subsequent - reactive. It is also important to adapt health policy to both the opportunities and the goals that it should have. The globalization achieved by the richest countries of the world does not bring, unfortunately, the progress and benefits of technological and economic progress to all people and nations, which is clearly evident in the deepening of the differences in the health insurance system among the population of developed and underdeveloped countries. In addition, it is important to indicate the interconnectedness of different branches in the process of globalization, so that the medical profession is directly dependent on the economic and financial processes, as well as the processes that take place in the legislation and the competencies of the ministries of public administration, but also for the work and social rights. It is therefore difficult to see all the effects of globalization on the medical profession, but it is important to have certain orientations on the direction in which the development is taking place, and how it is possible to accelerate the interaction with other, already mentioned processes.

2. CERTAIN CURRENTLY NOTED ISSUES IN HEALTHCARE SYSTEM OF REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

Certainly, in today healthcare it is necessary to take care of prevention, screening, nutrition, stop smoking, physical activities on individual basis in order to prevent health. But, on collective plan it is more difficult to manage all changes noted by globalisation in order to arrange sustainable development of this sector. Situation is not bright also looking from public health perspective and facts are showing that in 2016, 22,004 people died from the consequences of tumors in Republic of Serbia (Demographic yearbook 2016). If we are looking into this problem from a demographic point of view, it's a size of town in Serbia that disappears every year (in terms of number of people). Late diagnostics, or insufficient screening activities, insufficient education of the population for self-care are recognized as problems. Out of those 22,004 people, more than 9,000 are people who died in years of being able to work (Demographic yearbook 2016). According to some analyzes, close to 50% of these deaths can be prevented, and we have a steady increase in the number of new malignant tumors now at around 38,000 while a year ago it was 35,000. Treatment costs are high, and if you look at the costs of disability pensions, you will find that new disability pension beneficiaries are in fact 30% of people with a tumor (Statistical annual bilten, 2017). Hence, there is a huge systemic failure in many places because human lives are compromised due to large number of newly

diagnosed tumors, and those who survive these terrible diseases receive disability benefits, and they finally fall to the burden of the state and all citizens (tax payers). Also, more than 50,000 people annually pass from the consequences of a disease of the bloodstream, and again, if you look at the correlation with the beneficiaries of disability pensions - about 26% are just sick of these diseases and new users of disability pensions. In addition, officials report that 3.3 billion eur are spent on health care (approximately 10% of GDP of republic of Serbia). Due to the malpractice and corruption, it is suspected that almost 1 billion EUR is overpaid for medical services. Also, if we look at the work of institutions, about 30 health institutions are burdened with debt and 20 are in financial blockade (Bilten on information about financial business of healthcare institutions in Serbia , 2017). More than 50% of healthcare institutions ended last year in deficit (Bilten on information about financial business of healthcare institutions in Serbia ,2017). With approaching to the EU, more and more experts will emigrate what is being evidenced by the example of Croatia.

3. GLOBAL CHANGES IN LABOUR MARKET THAT AFFECTS HEALTHCARE INDUSTRY

Following the development of economic systems in the world, analyzing globalization and neoliberalism as a contemporary economic ideology, it is clear that at the global level there are needs for continuous modernization of society and economy. Two areas of exceptional importance, based on the principles of solidarity, which are directly influenced by the change of modern economic relations, are certainly - health and pension insurance. For the sake of sustainability, in the neoliberal market concept there is great pressure on society in order to change the concept of health and pension insurance. Modern organizational approaches to the healthcare system are associated with full-time jobs, and seem unsustainable as the future will require less and less labor. From Amy's robot assistant, through industrial robots, 3D printers, automated vehicles, computer algorithms, technology is changing mankind. According to the World Bank data, significant growth in sales of industrial robots is evident, while the Federation for Robotics (IFR) in the forthcoming period predicts the number of installations of new robots on an annual basis, with a two-digit annual growth rate. An increasing number of scientific papers speak in favor of robotization in terms of productivity incentives, wages, and even a positive impact on the labor market (education and dispersion of ownership). Although robotization represents a major, continuous change that occurs globally, Serbia faces additional problems such as: negative natural growth, age, population insufficient, gray economy, departure of young people for temporary or permanent residence abroad, which to a large extent it complicates the functioning and planning of a health system based on intergenerational solidarity. Looking at the new circumstances in the labor market (and some not so new), robotization is a major challenge for the whole society and requires a social consensus including healthcare systems future.

4. GLOBAL CHALLENGES AND PROBLEMS WITH THE AVAILABILITY OF DRUGS REFERRING TO CASE OF REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

Drug treatment is a key component in the implementation of human right to health. The World Health Organization believes that access to safe and affordable drugs is vital to maintaining the health standards of all. Innovative drugs appear on the markets of developed countries faster than ever and thus give hope to people suffering from rare, severe and incurable diseases. This opportunity should be accepted and provided with adequate therapy for everyone. Globally, since 2011, there has been a rapid development of new drugs in diabetes, as well as drugs for other indications. In Serbia it was a time of great financial restrictions and it was thought that in the field of innovative drugs it could "pass" by not having to be present in our country, that they are medicines from rich countries.

Subsequently, it turned out that Innovative drugs can significantly influence the benefit of treating the diseased because they carry new qualities and allow better control and reduced incidence of later complications. In certain disorders, the lack of timely therapy may lead to disability pension, and it also happens that caring for a particular patient means the obligation of a family member to leave the job. Pharmacoeconomic analyzes have shown that the cost of the disease, especially in chronic conditions with high incidence of illness, is usually significantly higher than the cost of prevention. Of course, there is a question of timely diagnostics, that is, prevention, regular systematic examinations and health education. From a bureaucratic point of view, in the process of being placed on the list of innovative drugs (and after registration), it is important that adequate pharmacoeconomic analysis was provided to demonstrate all the benefits of using a new medication viewed from an economic point of view. Then, special contracts are made that define the amount of drug that is planned for consumption as well as the ratio of participation in payment of medicines. On the other hand, for generic drugs, consumption approximation is often not adequate or significantly more drugs are consumed than planned. In this way, the budgetary funds can be spent more than planned and thus, for other activities healthcare state funds does not leave "financial space". Regulatory processes also directly and indirectly hinder innovative drugs to be found on the market. Extending the process of clinical studies in Serbia indirectly influences the deadline for registration of an innovative drug, therefore it is important to establish harmonization of regulations and avoid duplication of long-term procedures. A good example may be harmonization of regulations in clinical trials in the EU (voluntary harmonization procedure - VHP), which essentially avoids duplication of regulatory processes (Serbia is not part of that process unfortunately).

5. HEALTHCARE COOPERATIVES AS POTENTIAL MODEL THAT WOULD BE APPLIED THROUGH NEOLIBERALISM AND GLOBAL CHALLENGES

The health care system in the Republic of Serbia, based on the principle of solidarity, will not be able to withstand the pressure of over-development of the medical and pharmaceutical industries. And it will not be able to provide citizens in the long run with the services they are and what will be possible and necessary - thanks to development. As international organizations, such as the World Trade Organization, promote private forms of health insurance, the existence of healthcare cooperatives would be absolutely justified and in line with modern postulates, only that they would not be paid to the private owner - rather than the cooperative. Healthcare co-operatives, although almost completely forgotten today, is not a new model in our area. After the First World War, Serbia was devastated not only in the economic, but also in every other sense, including numerous medical and sanitary problems. The loss of doctors and professional personnel due to the war (today also happens due to migration) has particularly affected the rural regions. The creation of Serbian health cooperatives was initiated by Dr. Gavriilo Kojić with the aim of raising the quality and prevention of further health and sanitation problems, but also the problem of premature mortality and demography, ecological and sanitary, the problem of population education, and the development of the village (Jeremic, Nikolic 2000). Financing healthcare co-operatives (where a cooperative consisted of 300-500 families) was done through a membership fee, the amount of which would depend on the level of health insurance and the number of families insured. These cooperatives were initially formed with the support of the joint work of the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Social Policy and Public Health of the then Kingdom of SHS. However, the first idea of establishing a health care cooperative was created much earlier - at the First Congress of the Association of Agricultural Cooperatives in 1895. At that time, the founding of funds for aid to agricultural cooperatives began, so it was suggested that the issues of health and social protection of the rural population be solved in health cooperatives, but on the principles of

agricultural cooperatives. There is an inevitable connection with the economic cooperatives, in this case the agricultural sector. And then experts from around the world came to see what a miracle it was from healthcare cooperatives in poor Serbia. In the framework of health cooperatives, it was not only on curative, but also on prevention and education of the population, it influenced the construction of adequate waterworks, and the use of adequate food (today is the physical construction of infrastructure such as water supply network of local government domains, but the food issue is viewed a lot away from local self-government). In 1949, these cooperatives were involved in the public health system, and then, with the onset of ethatism, they were abolished. Today, when you look at the structure of disability pension beneficiaries and see that about 30% are the cause of disability pension tumors, and 26% - blood circulation, you discover what is the burden on the pension fund. The total number of these cases can be reduced by about 50 percent through the process of prevention and education, something similar to what healthcare co-operatives sometimes used in the field of infectious diseases. Secondly, an increasing number of retirees, and the longer life expectancy, and more and more advanced medicine will make it difficult for users of the pension to have an adequate modern quality of life, and all this together supports the thesis that healthcare cooperatives are useful. The health fund does not have to be separately monitored because it includes: health care and treatment, labor medicine, ecology, sanitary conditions that are now prescribed by standards, control of water, food, infrastructure in the area of operation of the cooperative, in particular the fields of prevention and curative activities. The other thing is that earlier people lived in the same places where they were produced, but all of this can be modified in a contemporary form because the goal is positive. At that time, they still had education against the white plague because the war was just over. This was also used by medical personnel, which is still necessary today (at the time of IMF measures when employment in budget institutions is stopped!). Also, there are numerous benefits of education that can go in different directions. It is a very interesting aspect of education in which children were monitored not only as infants, but also later in the pre-school and school age, and their proper development was directed both through curative and preventive measures.

6. CONCLUSION

Globalization is, by definition, a process interconnected with neoliberalism as ideology demonstrating significant requirements related to neoliberal economic concept in modern societies. As mentioned within introduction, the history of neo-liberalism as today's leading economic ideology is not long enough to draw the final conclusions, but it is of great importance to analyze the flows and impacts of this economic ideology in the context of market development and liberalization. Innovation should be nurtured, smart technology should create new jobs in healthcare, where our experts from the biomedical science will be employed. Introspective endogenous theory of economic growth, which introspectively deprives us of social development is future of development. The creation of a National Center for Medical Research can bring about 600 million eur annually according to some research. With the stopping of mismanagement in healthcare services, around half a billion euros could be saved. Only with those funds in a short time the health system would flourish! The process of denationalization of the health system (and insurance) will soon be required due to development of globalization and neoliberalism, and population need adequate model. Neoliberalism does not approve state participation anywhere, even in health care. Serbia needs to advance a health policy as well as a strategy for sustainable development of health and to prepare for the changes that we expect in healthcare. Within this paper, answer to global concerns in healthcare and economic development could be saw in healthcare cooperatives as there is noted concern for further sustainable development of healthcare institutions in models known so far, changes and new models needs to apply.

One of proposed models could be healthcare cooperatives, as this is model that is supporting basic principle of neoliberalism (it is market oriented model, privately owned and it is not monopolistic by its nature meaning it is supporting free competence). From the other hand this model should be governed by people itself (through managerial boards made on elections principle) therefore, their trust on this project should be highly developed. Also, implementation of this model would require additional research and pilot project implementation in order to understand all pre-requisites for successful governing. This kind of cooperatives can overcome many problems as healthcare system will not be able to provide citizens in the long run with the services they are and what will be possible and necessary - thanks to development. As international organizations, such as the World Trade Organization, promote private forms of health insurance, the existence of healthcare cooperatives would be absolutely justified and in line with modern postulates, only that they would not be paid to the private owner - rather than the cooperative.

LITERATURE:

1. Bilten on information about financial business of healthcare institutions in Serbia. Accessed: <http://www.komorazus.org.rs/downloads/Bilten/2017/Bilten%20br.%204%20Informacija%20o%20finansijskom%20poslovanju%20ZU%20za%20period%2001.01.-30.09.2017..pdf>. Apr2018
2. Demographic yearbook 2016, issued by Republic of Serbia, Republic Institute for Statistics, ISSN 0084-4357
3. Ibid.
4. Jeremic, V. Nikolic, A. 2000. Health cooperatives (1921-1949). Srpski arhiv za celokupno lekarstvo 2000, vol. 128, iss. 11-12, pp. 417-420
5. Stamenovic, M. Gulan, B, Dragas, B. Srbija Danas. Prometej NS 2017
6. Statistical annual bilten, Republic fund for pension and disability insurance of republic of Serbia. 2017 pp17-20